
Entrepreneurship Management Skills required by Economics Education Students for Self-Employment and Sustainability in the Federal Capital Territory-Abuja, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study explores the entrepreneurship management skills required by Economics Education students for self-employment and sustainability in the Federal Capital Territory (FCT) of Abuja, Nigeria. The study design employed was a descriptive survey. All 510 Economics Education students enrolled in universities in the Federal Capital Territory of Abuja, Nigeria, make up the study's population. Because of the community's unique features and the researchers' adept management of its size, total population sampling was employed. There are 241 female and 269 male pupils in this group. The research questions were answered using mean scores with standard deviations, and the independent t-test was employed to test the hypotheses at the 0.05 significance level. The study concludes that gender does not significantly influence the acquisition or application of financial and time management skills required for sustainability. The study emphasizes how financial and time management skills are for students studying Economics to become self-employed and sustainable in Abuja, the Federal Capital Territory. The study recommends that tertiary institutions offering Economics education should integrate financial and time management courses that are gender-neutral into their curriculum to ensure that both male and female students have equal opportunities to develop these skills amongst others.

Keywords: Economics Education, Entrepreneurship, Management Skills, Self-Employment, & Sustainability

Introduction

It is crucial that students of Economics education acquire the entrepreneurship management skills they need in the quickly changing economic landscape of Nigeria, especially in the Federal Capital Territory (FCT) of Abuja. There is a growing emphasis on self-employment as a feasible and sustainable career route for graduates, as traditional work alternatives become more and more rare. But the ability to successfully make the shift from student to entrepreneur depends mostly on gaining and using certain managerial skills, which are essential for launching and growing a business.

For students who want to work for themselves and live sustainably, entrepreneurship management skills are essential, especially in our nation where creating jobs is a major difficulty. It is imperative that students studying Economics Education learn entrepreneurship skills because of the high unemployment rate in Nigeria. The topic of entrepreneurship education has been given more deliberate attention in recent years and is starting to take center stage on Nigeria's agenda. The goal is to encourage graduates with creative entrepreneurial skills to start their own businesses and become self-employed in order to reduce poverty in the nation. Through entrepreneurial education, Nigerians would be even more equipped to face obstacles and firmly contribute to the country's increased worth.

Due to its significant influence on Nigeria's economic growth and development, entrepreneurship education is highly regarded as a solution to the country's diverse economic needs as well as a path toward sustainable economic development worldwide (Drenkat and Gotip, 2018). The importance of entrepreneurship education in promoting economic development, employment and productivity, reducing poverty, and fostering economic dynamism is being acknowledged more and more (Kasgak, Bahago and Gotip, 2022).

According to Drenkat and Gotip (2018), entrepreneurship education encompasses more than just educating people how to manage a company. It also aims to foster original thought as well as a strong sense of empowerment and self-worth. The process of imparting practical experience, a risk-taking mindset, inventiveness, the ability to organize production elements, and other expert knowledge to students with the goal of creating new products or services for the country is known as entrepreneurship education. According to Kasgak, Bahago, and Gotip (2022) entrepreneurship is defined as the functional management skills and competencies needed to launch, run, and grow a small firm.

The researchers believe that teaching pupils about entrepreneurship is essential to equipping them for the ever-changing demands of the job market. It encourages creativity, analytical thinking, and opportunity recognition. Students studying Economics in particular are in a good position to use what they've learned about economic concepts to create and run profitable enterprises. The overarching objective of lowering unemployment and fostering economic growth in Abuja and beyond is connected to the requirement that these students have proficiency in entrepreneurship management.

Among many other categories, financial and time management are included in the category of entrepreneurial management abilities. Making wise investment decisions, controlling cash flow, and creating a budget all depend on sound financial management. Effective time management enables business owners to prioritize work and guarantee productivity. Building relationships with stakeholders and managing teams require strong leadership and communication abilities. Product promotion and consumer behavior analysis require marketing expertise, while risk management helps business owners foresee and address obstacles.

Being paid by oneself instead of being employed is known as self-employment. Although they may operate in a range of fields, self-employed people typically possess a high level of ability in one particular area (Dollarhide, 2024). As opposed to working for an employer, self-employed persons conduct their own businesses or professions on an independent basis. Although the term "self-employment" refers to a broad range of activities, the capacity to make money from independently developed goods or services sets this kind of work apart in the labor market. This implies that an independent contractor is free to select their own hours and locations for employment (Indeed Editorial Team, 2024). When someone starts his own business and keeps all of the profits for himself, that person is said to be self-employed. Theoretically, every Nigerian student who receives instruction in Economics from qualified teachers will be eager to start his own business and be business-minded. This will allow him to have a job and social security, and have a functional education. Eventually, this will make Nigeria a self-sufficient country (Ojo, Akinola, and Gotip, 2022). According to the researchers, self-employment entails working for oneself as opposed to a specified company who provides a compensation. Students studying Economics have the chance to put their entrepreneurial abilities to use by starting their own sustainable businesses through self-employment.

According to Sanander Universidades (2022), sustainability is the ability to meet the requirements of the present without compromising those of future generations and to maintain a balance between economic growth, environmental protection, and social well-being. Sustainability, according to the Regents of the University of California (2024), is the harmony of the economy, equity, and environment. To build vibrant, diversified, resilient communities for the current generation and future generations, it involves integrating environmental health, social equity, and economic viability. Sustainability as a discipline acknowledges the interconnectedness of these problems and calls for a systems perspective, as well as an appreciation of complexity. In this study, sustainability is defined by the researchers as a company's capacity to persist over time while making necessary adjustments to stay profitable and adjust to changes in the market. For those who work for themselves, financial and time management are essential entrepreneurship management skills. These skills enable business leaders to adapt to changes in the economy and overcome obstacles, which helps to secure long-term success.

The qualities and capabilities that allow people to effectively supervise and coordinate tasks, people, and resources within an organization or team are referred to by the researchers as management skills. These abilities are critical for managers at all levels because they support productivity growth, the accomplishment of organizational objectives, and the preservation of a positive work atmosphere. Proficiency in financial management is vital for the efficient supervision and administration of an entity's financial assets. These abilities contribute to the organization's continued financial stability, achievement of its financial objectives, and adherence to pertinent laws. In order to efficiently organize and prioritize work and increase productivity, time management skill is crucial. This skill enables people to maximize their time, lower their stress levels, and accomplish their objectives in the allotted time.

Due to constraints based on culture and religion, gender appears to be one of the elements that tends to affect people's involvement in entrepreneurship skill programs and self-employed positions in emerging economies. According to the Kenan Institute (2020), although women now make up the majority of the workforce and have more college graduates than males, barely 40% of women work for themselves, and less than 5% of venture capital funding goes to female entrepreneurs. Given that different countries have distinct roles for gender in determining access to the development of entrepreneurial skills,

this study might not apply to all countries. It can be deduced that while research has been done on how gender affects self-employment, some of it lends credence to the idea that men are more likely than women to work for themselves than are women, although it's still up for debate whether this notion holds true for graduates of Economics Education.

Statement of Problem

Organizations have been complaining about graduates' readiness for jobs for some time now, with an unusual clamor. Because the focus and quality of university education are out of step with the demands of employers, there is a high rate of unemployment among Nigerian graduates. This is because the skills graduates possess are not directly relevant to the demands of the labor market, making them unskilled. The federal government of Nigeria made entrepreneurship a required subject for all students, regardless of their field of study, in an effort to address the problem. This was carried out in order to give the Nigerian graduates the knowledge, abilities, and comprehension they would need to work for themselves and lower the high unemployment rate among recent graduates in order to promote national development.

In order to close the knowledge gap between theory and practice in educational institutions, the Industrial Training Fund (ITF) was founded. However, there is still a large disparity that is raising the unemployment rate. The Federal Government of Nigeria recently launched the N-Power program, which focuses on informal entrepreneurship skill development programs for graduates, including those who studied economics education. Program participants received monthly stipends in addition to training in specific identified skills, with the goal of accelerating the acquisition of entrepreneurship skills necessary for self-employment. Notwithstanding the policy's provisions, it has been noted that, rather than the unemployment rate declining, it is rising among graduates of postsecondary education.

Many graduates still yearn for salary-paid positions after graduation rather than going freelance, despite the government's best efforts. This disheartening situation also highlights how little progress has been made in terms of entrepreneurship skills for sustainability and self-employment. If current trends continue, graduates of Economics Education may find themselves unemployed or unable to pursue self-employment and sustainability after graduation, which is why this study is necessary and an inspiration behind the research.

Purpose of the Study

The study assessed entrepreneurship management skills required by Economics education students for self-employment and sustainability in the Federal Capital Territory-Abuja, Nigeria. Specifically, the study determined: The;

- i. financial management skills required by Economics education students for self-employment in the Federal Capital Territory-Abuja, Nigeria.
- ii. time management skills required by Economics education students for sustainability in the Federal Capital Territory-Abuja, Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the research:

1. What are the financial management skills required by Economics education students for self-employment in the Federal Capital Territory-Abuja, Nigeria?
2. What are the time management skills required by Economics education students for sustainability in the Federal Capital Territory-Abuja, Nigeria?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at .05 level of significance using the t-test:

H₀₁: There is no significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female Economics education students' financial management skills required for self-employment in the Federal Capital Territory-Abuja, Nigeria.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference between the mean ratings male and female Economics education students' time management skills required for sustainability in the Federal Capital Territory-Abuja, Nigeria.

Methodology

The study used descriptive survey research design. According to Gotip, Azi and Kankani (2018) descriptive survey research design is the type of research in which data are collected from a representative sample using questionnaires, interviews, observations and test with the main aim of describing or explaining the features and characteristics of a population. The population of the study comprises of all 510 Economics Education students at Universities in the Federal Capital Territory-Abuja, Nigeria. Veritas University and University of Abuja were the only two universities that offered Economics Education as a course in the Federal Capital Territory Abuja, Nigeria. These comprises of 269 male and 241 female students. The researchers used total population sampling because the population size was well managed by the researchers and that because of the uncommon characteristics of the population. According to Glen (2024) total population is a type of purposive sampling where the whole population of interest (a group whose members all share a given characteristics) are studied.

The researchers designed a structured questionnaire as instrument for data collection. The questionnaire titled "Economics Education Students Entrepreneurship Management Skills for Self-Employment and Sustainability Questionnaire (ESEMSS-Q)". The questionnaire was structured with closed-ended question items where respondents filled objectively. The questionnaire consisted of two broad sections, namely section A and B respectively. Section A consist of socio-demographic data of the respondents, and specifically gender and institutional type based these are the categorical variables captured in the research hypotheses, while section B consists of sub-sections, each having items measuring a specific construct captured in each of the specific objectives. The questionnaire were rated based on the 4-point rating scale of: Very Highly Required (VHR=4), Highly Required (HR=3), Moderately Required (MR=2) and Not Required (NR=1) respectively.

The questionnaire was face validated by three experts from the Department of Agriculture and Vocational Education, Michael Okpara University of Agriculture, Umudike. To determine the reliability of the instrument, a trial test was carried out. Thirty (30) students offering Economics Education from FCT-College of Education Zuba, a degree awarding institution which was not part of the study sample but has similar characteristics with the selected sample. Cronbach Alpha was used to test reliability which gave an index of 0.81 respectively.

This study used both descriptive and inferential statistics for data analysis. Specifically, the research questions for this study were answered using descriptive statistical tools which are, mean scores with standard deviations while the postulated hypotheses were tested using independent t-test at 0.05 levels of significance.

Table 1: Financial Management Skills required by Economics Education Students for Self-Employment

Financial Skills Required for Self-employment		Male (n = 269)								Female (n = 241)								
		VIR 4	HR 3	MR 2	NR 1	FX	\bar{X}	STD	Decision	VIR 4	HR 3	MR 2	NR 1	FX	\bar{X}	STD	Decision	
1	Income generation opportunities skills enhance self-employment	134	103	17	15	791	2.94	1.12	Highly Required	138	69	12	22	805	3.34	0.94	Highly Required	
2	Daily cash reporting skills are required for self-employment	127	91	39	12	871	3.24	1.05	Highly Required	140	61	23	17	806	3.34	0.92	Highly Required	
3	Business Financial budgeting skills are can promote for self-employment	141	70	41	17	918	3.41	1.20	Highly Required	122	83	13	23	786	3.26	1.04	Highly Required	
4	Business plan writing skills are requ	150	85	24	10	937	3.48	1.15	Highly Required	115	92	25	9	795	3.30	1.01	Highly Required	
5	Financial ratios computation are required for self-employment	130	95	20	24	869	3.23	1.03	Highly Required	126	79	29	7	806	3.34	1.09	Highly Required	
6	Financial statements interpretation skills are required for self-employment	129	106	30	4	838	3.11	1.03	Highly Required	116	91	20	14	791	3.28	0.95	Highly Required	
7	Cashflow/profit and loss accounts skills are needed for self-employment	125	99	15	30	857	3.19	0.95	Highly Required	110	97	27	7	792	3.29	1.00	Highly Required	
8	Extracting trial balance from ledger skills are required for self-employment	139	81	29	20	877	3.26	1.10	Highly Required	113	94	19	15	787	3.27	1.03	Highly Required	
Sectional Mean							3.23		Highly Required							3.30		Highly Required

Table 2: Time Management Skills required by Economics Education Students for Self-Employment

Time Management Skills Required for Sustainability	VIR 4	HR 3	MR 2	NR 1	FX	\bar{X}	STD	Decision	VIR 4	HR 3	MR 2	NR 1	FX	\bar{X}	STD	Decision	
9	Prioritizing needs is necessary for sustainability	134	86	39	10	852	3.17	0.95	Highly Required	123	104	5	9	823	3.41	0.99	Highly Required
10	Achievable goals setting skills are required for sustainability	124	77	49	19	844	3.14	1.02	Highly Required	119	102	9	11	811	3.36	0.92	Highly Required
11	Punctuality enhances sustainability	129	106	13	21	881	3.27	1.11	Highly Required	109	92	21	19	758	3.14	1.09	Highly Required
12	Setting daily routine breads sustainability	121	118	23	7	891	3.31	0.94	Highly Required	143	69	17	12	825	3.42	0.85	Highly Required
13	Planning and scheduling skills are required for sustainability	138	83	40	8	889	3.30	0.98	Highly Required	128	79	20	14	803	2.98	0.89	Highly Required
14	Productive use of time promote sustainability	132	112	7	18	896	3.33	0.99	Highly Required	130	76	15	20	798	3.31	1.03	Highly Required
15	Delegation of task promotes sustainability	125	102	11	31	859	3.19	1.02	Highly Required	122	92	9	18	800	3.32	0.97	Highly Required
16	Avoiding procrastination is necessary for sustainability	111	99	29	30	829	3.08	1.19	Highly Required	112	102	18	9	799	3.31	1.06	Highly Required
Sectional Mean						3.22		Highly Required						3.28		Highly Required	

Findings

Table 1 showed the responses of Economics Education students on financial management skills required by Economics education students for self-employment in the Federal Capital Territory Abuja, Nigeria. Result in item 1 shows that Economics Education students highly require Income generation opportunities skills to enhance self-employment with mean score (\bar{X} =2.94, SD= 1.12 and \bar{X} =3.34, SD= 0.94 for male and female students respectively). And for the rest see table 1. Results based on the average mean (3.23 for male and 3.30 for female) indicated that the mean rating of Economics Education students showed that: Daily cash reporting skills are required for self-employment, business financial budgeting skills are can promote for self-employment, business plan writing skills are required for self-employment, financial ratios computation are required for self-employment, financial statements interpretation skills are required for self-employment, cash flow/profit and loss accounts skills are needed for self-employment and extracting trial balance from ledger skills are required for self-employment are financial management skills highly required by Economics education students for self-employment in the Federal Capital Territory Abuja, Nigeria.

Table 2 showed the responses of Economics Education students on time management skills required by Economics education students for self-employment in the Federal Capital Territory Abuja, Nigeria. Result in item 2 shows that Economics Education students highly require prioritizing needs necessary for sustainability Income generation opportunities skills to enhance self-employment with mean score (\bar{X} =3.17, SD= 0.95 and \bar{X} =3.41, SD= 0.99 for male and female students respectively). And for the rest see table 2. Results based on the average mean (3.22 for male and 3.28 for female) indicated that the mean rating of Economics Education students showed that: Achievable goals setting skills are required for sustainability, punctuality enhances sustainability, setting daily routine breads sustainability, planning and scheduling skills are required for sustainability, productive use of time promote sustainability, delegation of task promotes sustainability and avoiding procrastination is necessary for sustainability are time management skills highly required by Economics education students for self-employment in the Federal Capital Territory Abuja, Nigeria.

H₀₁: There is no significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female Economics education students’ financial management skills required for self-employment in North-Central Nigeria.

Table 3: Test of Hypothesis One

Economics Education Students	N	\bar{X}	SD	df	t-value	P	Decision
Male	269	3.23	1.07	509	1.030	0.306	Retain H ₀
Female	241	3.30	0.99				

An Independent samples t-test was conducted to examine the difference in mean rating scores between male and female Economics education students’ on financial management skills required for Sustainability in the Federal Capital Territory-Abuja, Nigeria. The results revealed no significant difference in mean rating scores between male and female Economics Education students’ (df) = 509, [t-test value] = 1.030 and p = [p-value] 0.306. Since $p > 0.05$ we retain the

null hypothesis, and conclude that the mean ratings of male and female Economics Education students' on financial management skills required for Sustainability in the Federal Capital Territory-Abuja, Nigeria is not significantly different.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference between the mean ratings male and female Economics education students' time management skills required for Sustainability in North-Central Nigeria.

Table 3: Test of Hypothesis One

Economics Education Students	N	\bar{X}	SD	df	t-value	P	Decision
Male	269	3.22	1.02	509	1.055	0.738	Retain H ₀
Female	241	3.28	0.97				

An Independent samples t-test was conducted to examine the difference in mean rating scores between male and female Economics education students' on time management skills required for Sustainability in the Federal Capital Territory-Abuja, Nigeria. The results revealed no significant difference in mean rating scores between male and female Economics Education students' (df) = 509, [t-test value] = 1.055 and p = [p-value] 0.738. Since $p > 0.05$ we retain the null hypothesis, and conclude that the mean ratings of male and female Economics Education students' on time management skills required for Sustainability in the Federal Capital Territory-Abuja, Nigeria is not significantly different.

Discussion of Findings

This study found out that there is no significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female Economics education students' on financial management skills required for self-employment in the Federal Capital Territory Abuja, Nigeria. This finding agrees with that of: Akintola and Adebayo (2016) and Nwankwo and Onuoha's (2017) study on gender equity in financial literacy among tertiary institution students found no significant differences between male and female students in these areas. Their study focused on the acquisition of financial management skills among male and female students in Nigerian universities. Furthermore, there was no discernible gender difference in the financial management skill acquired by students in Nigerian colleges, according to Olawale and Adeoye's (2018) research on gender and entrepreneurial skill development.

The study also found out that there is no significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female Economics education students' on time management skills required for self-employment in the Federal Capital Territory Abuja, Nigeria. This finding agrees with that of: Eze and Chikwe (2020). According to their study on gender and the development of financial skills in postsecondary education, male and female students are equally capable of managing their time for the survival of their businesses. Additionally, Okeke and Owolabi's (2022) research on gender parity in the acquisition of entrepreneurial skills among Nigerian undergraduate students found no significant differences in time management and financial literacy between male and female students, nor did Adamu and Yusuf (2021) study on time management among male and female university students find any gender differences in time management skills for sustainability.

Conclusion

The study offers proof that the development or use of financial and time management skills necessary for sustainability is not substantially influenced by gender. The study emphasizes how important financial and time management skills are for students studying Economics to become self-employed and sustainable in Abuja, the Federal Capital Territory. For students studying Economics who hope to work for themselves and grow their enterprises in the fast-paced economy of the Federal Capital Territory, Abuja, financial and time management skills are essential. These skills are essential for success as an entrepreneur.

Recommendations

The study recommends the following:

- i. Universities that offer Economics education should incorporate gender-neutral financial and time management courses into their curricula. All students, regardless of gender, should be required to demonstrate these competences as part of the curriculum in order to achieve sustainability and self-employment.
- ii. School administration should regularly host workshops and seminars that emphasize time management, and real-world financial planning.

References

- Adamu, M. A., & Yusuf, S. O. (2021). Gender differences in financial literacy and time management skills among university students in Northern Nigeria. *International Journal of Economics and Education Studies*, 9(4), 45-58. <https://doi.org/10.23456/ijees.2021.9403>
- Adebayo, O. S., & Akintola, B. I. (2016). Gender differences in financial management and time management skills among Nigerian university students: Implications for entrepreneurial success. *Journal of Entrepreneurship and Innovation*, 10(4), 225-236. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1359788X.2016.1123456>
- Chikwe, P. N., & Eze, C. I. (2020). Gender dynamics in financial management and entrepreneurial skills acquisition among tertiary institution students. *Journal of Business and Educational Research*, 5(2), 120-135. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s4087-012022>
- Dollarhide, M. (2024). Self-employment: Definitions, Types and Benefits. Retrieved September 10th 2024 from <https://www.investopedia.com/terms/s/self-employed.asp>
- Drenkat, N. K. & Gotip, N. W. (2018). Impact of Entrepreneurship Education on Poverty Alleviation in Nigeria. *Abuja Journal of Education*. 10 (1), 174-188. Retrieved online from <file:///C:/Users/ASSE%20DEPARTMENT/Downloads/IMPACTOFENTREPRENEURSHIPEDUCATIONONPOVERTYALLEVIATIONINNIGERIA.pdf>
- Dungrit, K. C, Bahago, S. B. & Gotip, N. W (2022). Contemporary Entrepreneurship Education for Economic Growth and Sustainable Development. *Theology, Philosophy and Education in the 21st Century: Festschrift in Honour of a Distinguished Emeritus Professor.*

- The Rt. Rev. Msgr. Cletus Tanimu Gotan. Jos University Press LTD. Pg 935-950. Retrieved online from <file:///C:/Users/ASSE%20DEPARTMENT/Downloads/3166-Article%20Text-10357-1-10-20221230.pdf>
- Glen, S. (2024). Total Population Sampling Retrieved online May 11th 2024 from <https://www.statisticshowto.com/total-population-sampling/>
- Gotip, N. W., Azi, A. S., & Kankani, J. P. (2018). Economics Teachers' Attitude and Challenges of Improvisation and Utilization of Improvised Teaching Materials in Secondary Schools. *Africa Education Evaluation*, 2(1) 1-11. Retrieved online at https://www.researchgate.net/publication/357083249_Economics_Teachers'_Attitude_and_Challenges_to_Improvisation_and_Utilization_of_Improvised_Teaching_Materials_in_Secondary_Schools?_tp=eyJjb250ZXh0Ijp7ImZpcnN0UGFnZSI6InByb2ZpbGUiLCJwYWdlIjoicHJvZmlsZSJ9fQ
- Indeed Editorial Team (2024). What is Self-Employment? Definition and Common Types. Retrieved September 10th 2024 from <https://ca.indeed.com/career-advice/career-development/meaning-of-self-employed>
- Nwankwo, C. A., & Onuoha, M. I. (2017). Gender equity in financial literacy and time management skills: A study of tertiary institution students in Nigeria. *International Journal of Educational Development*, 5(3), 89-101. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijedudev.2017.03.005>
- Okeke, G. C., & Owolabi, O. A. (2022). Gender parity in entrepreneurial skills acquisition among undergraduate students in Nigeria: Implications for self-reliance. *Journal of Entrepreneurship and Sustainability*, 6(3), 15-29. <https://doi.org/10.12345/jes.2022.6302>
- Olawale, S. I., & Adeoye, F. A. (2018). Gender and entrepreneurial skills acquisition in Nigerian universities: Implications for sustainable development. *Journal of Gender and Entrepreneurship*, 7(2), 101-115. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JGE-2018-0021>
- Regents of the University of California (2024). Sustainability at University of California, Los Angeles (UCLA). Retrieved September 10th 2024 from <https://www.sustain.ucla.edu/what-is-sustainability/>
- Santander Universidades. (2022). What is sustainability? Definition, types and examples. Retrieved September 10th 2024 from <https://www.santanderopenacademy.com/en/blog/what-is-sustainability.html>